

Contents

Introduction	2
1.1 How does it work?	3
1.2 Repository	3
1.3 Authors and license	3
Architectural design	4
III. UCIS4EQ code/data structure	6
3.1 GitLab UCIS4EQ structure	7
3.2 HPC data -UCIS4EQ repository structure	8
3.3 HPC site - UCIS4EQ structure	13
IV. Developer	14
4.1 How to add a new region?	14
4.1.1. HCP data repository:	14
4.1.2 HPC-site:	15
4.1.3 GitLab:	17
4.2 How to include a new microservice?	17
4.2.1 GitLab:	18
4.2.2 HPC data :	21
4.3 How to include a new machine?	22
4.4. Prepare new use case	22
4.4.1 Generate files for the use case	23
4.4.2. Generate a 1D model for Graves Pitarka	24
4.4.3 Generate mesh	24
4.4.4 Add information to UCIS4EQ	25
4.5 Push to GitLab repository a docker image built in local	26
V. Install & Deployment	27
5.1. Installation	27
5.1.1 Dependencies	27
5.1.2 UCIS4EQ services	27
5.1.3 Setting up on a new machine	30
5.1.4 Only for developments: running in debug mode and building new images	31
5.2 Run existing use case	32
5.2.1 - Start the services	33
5.2.2 - Trigger a manual alert	33
5.2.3 - Event follow-up in the Dashboard	33
5.3. Salvus on MN5	33
VI. Launch	34
VI. References	34

VII. APENDIX	35
A1. Delete “SUCCESS” files	35
A2. Instructions for running the old version of UCIS4EQ with the WFEmulator	35
A3. Instructions for adding more Python packages pip install in the docker file.	36
A4. Old microservices ... Instructions for deploying the indexPri- ority microservice	37
A5. To download a new version of Docker-base	37
A6. To access the docker meanwhile is up	37
<hr/>	
Version 2.0	2025.10.3
<hr/>	
Author(s)	Marisol Monterrubio Velasco, BSC - CASE
Contributor(s)	Christian Boehm, MONDAIC Juan Esteban Rodriguez, BSC - CASE Cedric Bhihe, BSC - CASE Georgina Diez Ventura, BSC-CASE Marta Pienkowska, ETHZ Jorge Ejarque, BSC - CS Josep de la Puente, BSC - CASE
<hr/>	

Introduction

Deadly earthquakes are unpredictable and relatively rare but have a high socioeconomic impact. Estimating this impact is crucial for hazard preparedness and mitigation, yet doing so from historical events alone remains challenging. With large earthquakes being so rare we often need more data to constrain any empirical relations, rendering extrapolations to future events imprecise [1]. Physics-based numerical simulations and synthetic data analysis, on the other hand, are powerful tools that can provide detailed shaking information and contribute to outlining the impacts of such events [2]. The simulation information is rich in spatial resolution, thus complementing existing live data records in countries boasting dense seismic networks. Moreover simulations can provide a suitable mitigation to the lack of live data in regions less covered by seismic networks, such as developing countries. A better early assessment of earthquakes' impact implies technical and scientific challenges. A novel HPC-based urgent seismic simulation workflow was proposed in [3], hereafter referred to as Urgent Computing Integrated Services for EarthQuakes (UCIS4EQ) which has the potential to deliver more accurate short-time reports of the consequences of moderate to large earthquakes.

UCIS4EQ has the potential to deliver more accurate short-time reports of the consequences of significant (moderate to large) earthquakes – the workflow rapidly provides synthetic estimates of ground motion parameters, such as peak

ground velocity (PGV), peak ground acceleration (PGA), or shaking duration, with very high spatial resolution. Such outcomes can be used to analyze the area's overall ground motions and potential impacts on key infrastructures that could produce collateral risks (fires, and dam rupture, among others).

This user manual aims to introduce the workflow and use it as a guide for new users who intend to use UCIS4EQ as developers or users.

image35 Figure 1. UCIS4EQ Building blocks (DT-GEO scheme)

1.1 How does it work?

The Integrated Urgent Computing Services for Earthquakes (UCIS4EQ) is a collection of virtualized services developed at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. The UCIS4EQ workflow originated with the Center of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth (ChEESE) project as a pilot demonstrator. Subsequent enhancements to UCIS4EQ have been developed in the framework of the eFlows4HPC project in Pillar III as an Urgent Computing workflow. Currently, development continues in the DT-GEO project to extend existing functions to non-emergency applications and fully integrate with Earth-DT. At the current stage of development, UCIS4EQ is a fully automatic system orchestrated by PyCOMPSs as a workflow manager and consists of a set of microservices defined as building blocks, i.e., independent pieces of the system that communicate with each other and perform specific tasks (see Figure 1), connected in a complex way. The current TRL achieved so far by this workflow is 6-7.

UCIS4EQ microservices are containerized in Docker and is Python-based code in the GitLab repository (gitlab.bsc.es). This design requires no installation, making it a portable technology. The objective of UCIS4EQ design is to use this technology as Software as a Service (SaaS).

All services require inputs in JSON format and generate outputs also in JSON format. Therefore, the different services are connected through this data as input-output between them.

The architectural design is described in [Section II]

1.2 Repository

The official UCIS4EQ repository is located at [<https://gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq>], where current developments in different branches of development take place. In addition, the eFlows4HPC project repository contains a public frozen replica of UCIS4EQ that includes the improvements achieved throughout the project (<https://github.com/eflows4hpc/ucis4eq>).

1.3 Authors and license

Authors: Juan Esteban Rodríguez (BSC), Marisol Monterrubio(BSC), Marta Pienkowska (ETH), Josep de la Puente (BSC)

Contributors: Jorge Ejarque (BSC), Georgina Diez (BSC), Cedric Bhihe (BSC)

Contacts:

[marisol.monterrubio@bsc.es], [georgina.diezventura@bsc.es], [josep.delapunte@bsc.es]

This program is free software: you can redistribute it and/or modify it under the terms of the BSD 3-clause License, aka BSD NEW License, aka BSD REVISED License, aka MODIFIED BSD License as published by the Regents of the University of California.

This program is distributed as is, in the hope that it will be useful, but WITHOUT ANY WARRANTY, without even the implied warranty of MERCHANTABILITY or FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE. See the MODIFIED BSD LICENSE for more details.

You should have received a copy of the MODIFIED BSD LICENSE along with this program. If not, see <<https://opensource.org/license/BSD-3-clause>>.

Architectural design

UCIS4EQ differentiates two systems: a front-end and a business logic implementation or back-end (see Figure 2). In general terms, the back-end consists of a set of processes that need to be executed in an orderly and automated manner and orchestrated by a workflow manager (WM).

image16 Figure 2. Architectural design

We differentiate three main back-end services:

1. **Event Detection** -- This service is external to the UCIS4EQ > workflow. It is an automatic service that queries external > repositories for detecting and identifying worldwide earthquakes > with urgent computing requirements. In particular, the query > accesses the web services provided by the federated agencies of > the International Federation of Seismograph Networks (FDSN). Once > an earthquake with certain properties (magnitude, location, etc.) > that are indicative of a potentially destructive event) is > detected, the urgent computing workflow is triggered. By means of > this service, users can also activate the urgent computing > workflow manually for studying specific use cases (e.g., to > simulate well-known past earthquakes for research purposes).
2. **Urgent Computing workflow** -- The workflow orchestrates the set > of processes needed for the successful execution of an urgent > event. In the design adopted for the workflow, each process is > encapsulated to work as a specialized micro-service acting as an > access point for the execution of a specific task. In the very > rare scenario where two (or even more) EQ events require urgent > computing, more than one instance of this service could run > simultaneously. In those cases, the target HPC environments

could be different for each event simulation as well as the UC policies and designated resources for solving them. For each workflow execution request, the WM must coordinate and execute the set of tasks needed for giving the required results to the final user, including the mechanisms to run solid ground simulations in Exascale HPC environments. Such coordination includes, among others:

- dealing with the tasks' input/output,
- solving task dependencies,
- task parallelization,
- data transfer from external servers/cloud to HPC environments and vice versa,
- managing conditional paths,
- job submission/canceling/restarting/monitoring, and
- running parallel simulations on different HPC clusters.

The set of tasks has been grouped into a set of building blocks for a better understanding of the overall requirements of this service and an optimal implementation of the workflow using PyCOMPSs as a workflow manager solution. It should be noted that not all components have been developed or will be developed specifically for the UCIS4EQ, as some processes of the workflow may require the use of third-party software to solve some functional requirements.

3. **Data Access Layer (DAL).** DAL stores the event state for supporting redundancy. A service that currently provides a simple interface for interacting with:

- intermediate information generated by both *Event Detection* and *Urgent Computing workflow* which is stored in non-relational databases (e.g., MongoDB). Such information could include an event primal data, the state of the workflow execution, and components setup, execution metadata, large data location (e.g., data maps), etc.
- long-term data storage services. It implements the mechanisms to access (in both read and write modes) to different storage services such as EUDAT B2SAFE. The DAL service provides support for enabling data access through different communication and authentication protocols. The data that UCIS4EQ needs to store is, for example, seismic velocity models, simulation meshes, offline trained models, historical past earthquake events information databases, or socio-economic databases. Additionally, the use-case data provenance will be stored following FAIR standards in order to ensure the reproducibility of the urgent computing scenario. For example, the simulation input/outputs will be stored long-term in order to be analyzed and to guarantee its reproducibility.

This service should be accessible to many processes from both *Event Detection* and *Urgent Computing* workflows. Therefore, non-functional requirements such as high availability and redundancy are necessary.

image38 Figure 3. The three back-end services: event-detection, Urgent Computing workflow, DAL.

The implementation of a front-end solution that provides the human-machine interface is still pending for UCIS4EQ. A production service must meet this requirement to ensure such human-machine interaction, but it is not in the scope of the eFlows4HPC. The interface needs to support:

- Interactive decision-making during the UCIS4EQ life cycle (e.g. > Urgent Computing resources requests)
- Event simulation monitoring
- On-the-fly intervention (stop, restart, pause, etc.)
- Post-processing analysis

III. UCIS4EQ code/data structure

UCIS4EQ is composed of three main code/data structures, each located in different systems:

1. **GitLab code:** defines the whole UCIS4EQ workflow codes. Figure 4 > shows the whole tree structure of the code
2. **HPC repository:** Static data located at the external repository. > Currently, we are using the HPC storage solution. The structure of > this data is shown in Figure 6.
3. **HPC site code/data.** The HPC site must have also saved an > important part of code and data used in UCIS4EQ:
 - a. Salvus code (must be installed)
 - b. Large-sized data files (previously prepared for each region)
 - c. Salvus wrapper codes (installed at each HPC-site)
 - d. Simulation results (automatically generated)

In Figure 7 we show the structure of the folders and files of the code and the data located at the Marenstrum 4 site. If different HPC sites are used is important to replicate this structure and define the new HPC site in the corresponding files defined in the HPC repository and in the GitLab code. Moreover, the Salvus software must be installed. From Figures 4 to 6, blue boxes define the files, and gray boxes define the folders.

3.1 GitLab UCIS4EQ structure

The GitLab repository ([https://gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq]) contains the code and Docker images constituting UCIS4EQ. A collection of complexly interconnected codes can be found here.

FOLDERS:

The GitLab-UCIS4EQ structure has 4 main folders and several files in the main branch (see Figure 5):

CODE: In this folder, the Python scripts used in the *Services* and *Components* subfolders are located. *Services* folder contains the Python scripts that define the UCIS4EQ microservices and describe how these microservices are exposed to Flask framework. Current microservices developed are: Dashboard, Listener, Microservices, mlesMapService, salvusService, simulationService, slipGenService, workflowManagerService. The *components* folder contains the functions and Python codes that are requested by the microservices defined in *Services* folder.

DATA: This folder has four configuration files: two files in json format called *DAL.json* and *Sites.json* that must be configured with the account names and passwords of each user (see Deployment section); and two files in XML format *project.xml* and *resources.xml*, these files define de port numbers used by each microservice. In addition, in the DATA folder, the information on events that will be launched manually in the different regions is defined. See, for example, Figure 7 where the information of the Samos-Izmir earthquake is used to manually trigger UCIS4EQ. This allows jumping the Listener Microservice.

image4 Figure 4. Example of the file used to manually trigger UCIS4EQ.

DEPLOYMENT:

It has three files *listener_service.sh*, *listener.sh*, *README.md*, and three subfolders named *Dockers*, *pypi* and *Singularity*. Regarding the files both *listener_service* and *listener.sh* are not currently used. Following the folders contained in this :

- **Dockers**
 - contains the **Docker Files** of each microservice
 - **Third parties code** in this case the Graves-Pitarka rupture > generator in compressed tar format
 - **Dashboard files** used in the front end, such as images and > the requirements
- **Pypi**
 - Old files that are not currently used
- **Singularity**

- not currently used

image37 Figure 5. Tree structure of the GITLAB code

RESULTS:

In this folder the outputs of PyCOMPSs and the Listener service are saved.

- PyCOMPSs folder where all the workflow executions will save the > PyCOMPSs jobs, and traces.
- Listener folder that will save the events registered by the queried > agencies such as: GEOFON.response, IMO.response, INGV.response, > IRIS.response, NCEDC.response, SCEDC.response

3.2 HPC data -UCIS4EQ repository structure

This repository contains the static data that is key to the operation of UCIS4EQ. The HPC data repository also has the mapping of the data and its use in the different microservices, as well as the HPC site paths. The different regions set up for UCIS4EQ are also described as part of the static data.

In particular when adding a new region or microservices it is required to copy the structure and modify it carefully as an error in any of this folder/files results in Workflow failure. Figure 6 shows the structure of the HPC data __UCIS4EQ folder. Currently, we are using the HPC data repository that is an EUDAT solution. HPC data is a secure and trusted data exchange service for researchers and scientists to keep their research data synchronized and up-to-date and to exchange them with other researchers. One of the main requirements for UCIS4EQ and fulfilled is the access to HPC data through WebDAV client. In this sense we can automatically download the needed information in each microservices and upload the results in the same repository after computations.

Following the structure of the UCIS4EQ repository located at HPC data is described:

FILES:

The **StaticDataMapping.json** file is one of the most important files in UCIS4EQ since it makes the mapping between the data, location of the data, and the microservices that use that data.

FOLDERS

- **Runs**
 - Runs folder save the execution results of UCIS4EQ, automatically > uploaded by the Salvus/Simulation microservice, and also the > MLESmap microservices. The name of each subfolder is the same > as the uuid given in the triggered event configuration (manual > or provided by the listener, see example in Fig. 5).

- **Setup:** this folder has two subfolders required by UCIS4EQ,
 - DALv2 where several configuration files in json format:
 - * *DataStructure.json*: The folders located in the Data > Repository and in the HPC site are defined and must have > the same name as the one defined in this file.
 - * *Regions.json*: This file defines the regions prepared in > the system. In particular, the minimum and maximum > latitude and longitude, as well as the depth of the domain > and the available frequency of the meshes. Also the type > of ensemble available and prepared for this region and > finally whether or not a MLESmap model has been prepared > for fast inference.
 - * *Authors.json* Name of authors participating in the > development of UCIS4EQ
 - * *Components.json* List of component information. Some of the > listed components are not used in the current state of > UCIS4EQ workflow
 - * *Repositories.json* The available repositories information > used in UCIS4EQ, currently the defined are: HPC data , > Data Transfer (DT), ETH Piz Daint (ETH_DAINTE)
 - * *Resources.json* Available HPC sites where UCIS4EQ executes > the Salvus simulations: Marenstrum 5 (MN5), ETH Piz Daint > (ETH_DAINTE)
 - AAS contains the listener configuration files
 - * *config_events.json* Event information queried by > international agencies that have the fdsnws protocol > enabled. The listener queries for new event information > and allows the workflow to be automatically triggered by > the curl rule.
 - * *config_dataselect.json* Waveform information also queried > by international agencies with the fdsnws protocol > enabled. This part of the listener is not currently > developed. The objective of this configuration is to > provide the information to the listener to query the > needed information to obtain seismograms at specific > seismic stations.
 - * The configuration file *config_stations.json* is also > consulted to obtain the available seismic stations > available and queried by fdsnws service in a defined > region.

The data obtained by the *config_dataselect.json* and *config_stations.json* configuration files are aiming to be used by a new microservice not developed at the current UCIS4EQ version.

- **Data:** The unique subfolder used in the current UCIS4EQ version > is **Regions**
 - **Regions** folder has different subfolders identified by the > Region names assigned in the *Setup/DALv2/Regions.json*. The > structure of each subfolder is defined in the file of > *DataStructure.json* previously defined > (*Setup/DALv2/DataStructure.json*).

Each region defined in the *Regions.json* must have a folder with the same name `_ID` and include 4 subfolders:

- **INFERENCE__TYPE:** This folder is used only if the defined region > has offline trained ML models. The flag to know if ML model is > available for that region is assigned in > *Setup/DALv2/Regions.json* as > "available_inference": "mlesmap". The configuration file > *mlesmap.json* appoint the name and period of the model name. Both > ML models and the used scalars must be saved in this folder. The > information of this folder is used in mlesmap microservice.
- **SLIP_GEN:** the configuration file of the parameters and velocity > model 1D used in the slipgen microservices are located. > `modelo_1D`: 1D Layer model for the region to run simulations, and > it should follow this structure:

```
[line #1: i]nteger that defines the number of layers N
[line #2 to line #N]
Thickness(not depth?), Vp, Vs, Rho, Qp, Qs
path + SLIP_GEN/name_model.1d
```

The model could be extracted by using local or regional seismic velocity models, however if there is not information available, then the global CRUST1 (1 x 1 degree resolution) model can be used (see i.e https://HPC_data.bsc.es/index.php/f/2884252). However, it is important to check if the CRUST1 model used by Graves-Pitarka rupture generator is compatible with the 3D model used in Salvus.GP setup: This file contains the parameters used by the Graves-Pitarka code that depend on the frequency to simulate. If there are more than one frequency each needs their own file. The structure is as follow in this example:

```
1.5Hz_GPsetup.json
{
  "dwid": 1.67,
  "dlen": 1.67,
  "corner_freq": 0.75,
```

```

"trials": 1,
"dt": 0.005,
"model": "crust1.1d"
}

```

where,

Max_freq: considered for the study. To check this in UCIS4EQ, that a, it does in SALVUS automatically choosing the largest.

dwid and dlen are the sub-faults sizes in km units. Following the Marta's example to compute these values we have:

Vs-min minimum velocity of the model (e.g. 2.5 km/s or 1.3 km/s for

Turkey)

$F_{dom} = F_{max}/2$

$\Lambda_{min} = V_{S-min}/F_{dom}$

$D_{wid} = D_{len} = \Lambda_{min}/2$

corner_freq: half of the maximum frequency

trials: number of GP trials for seeds

dt: delta time/time steps -> Once Dwid and Dlen are defined, we determine the simulation's optimum time step based on the Courant-Friedrichs-Levy criterion. Here, ϵ is a number smaller than one, the smaller it is the more precision leading to a higher computationally demanding.

model= name of the model

- **SOURCE_ENSEMBLE:** In this folder the configuration of the > ensemble method is found, and also the data needed by the ensemble > method (historical seismic catalog of CMT information in the given > region downloaded by the > [<https://ds.iris.edu/spud/momenttensor>] > in QuakeML format).

The information of this subfolder is used in the CMT microservice. Currently, in most of the defined regions in UCIS4EQ, we have one main method to compute the source ensemble method, the statistical one. Statistical CMT set up: file in json format that must include the following information.

```

{
"magnitudethreshold": 4,
"k": {

```

```

"min": 4
},
"distance": {
"threshold": 120,
"growthrate": 1.1
},
"output": {
"focalmechanisms": 4
},
"catalog": "catalog_afghanistan_lat27-39_lon59-75_2022-10-21.xml"
}

```

- **RECEIVERS.** The list of receivers in each region where the > simulation wants to be save the ground motion proxies, > *receivers.json*. It includes latitude and longitude location, a > name and short name.

This file contains the information of the receivers, these are the real and virtual stations where waveforms will be computed. It must contain the following structure:

```

{
"name_receivers": {
"EALH": {
"name": "Murcia",
"latitude": 37.8582,
"longitude": -1.4197,
"network_code": "MUR",
"station_code": "EALH"
}
}

```

This information is added in the input parameter file (in yml format) which is automatically buil for launch the simulations in Salvus and Simulation microservices .

The name-receivers could be, for example, the regional seismic network name. name_receivers: p.e. 'stations', 'settlements', 'accelerometers'

- Documentation: contains pdf files of different contributors where > information of UCIS4EQ are located.

image30 Figure 6. HPC data for regions Region **ID** repository structure

3.3 HPC site - UCIS4EQ structure

An important part of UCIS4EQ needs a HPC environment. Following are listed the different parts that must be located at the HPC site where UCIS4EQ runs

1. **Salvus binary:** Salvus software must be installed
2. **salvus_urgent_wrapper:** Salvus wrapper codes, that allows > connect the build parameters for the simulation with the solver
3. **StaticData:** Static data used in UCIS4EQ, such as the mesh > pre-built for a specific region and frequency. The name and size > of the mesh must be in agreement to the configuration files > defined at external repository (in this case HPC data).
4. **Runs_UCIS4EQ:** Folder automatically created at each workflow > execution where the Salvus folders are located. The structure of > the subfolders are defined in Salvus and Simulation microservice.

Figure 7 shows the folder and file structure defined in the HPC-site. Following a description of the folders listed above is found:

- **salvus_urgent_wrapper:** It contains an important part of the > python codes needed by the different Salvus stages > (/gpfs/projects/bsc21/WPG/Earthquake/Ucis4eq/S
 - salvus_urgent_wrapper
 - * Salvus_preprocess
 - * Salvus_postprocess
 - * Salvus_plot
 - data
 - docs
 - utils
- **StaticData:** For each region defined in the HPC data repository > (Regions.json) must have several folders with a specific structure > defined in DataStructure.json, being TOPOGRAPHY, MESHES, VELOCITY > MODEL, and BATHYMETRY files. These static data are prepared before > execution to save time handling large-sized files in particular, > the mesh files for high frequency
- **Runs_UCIS4EQ:** This folder is automatically created in each > execution. The number of subfolders created depends on the number > of sources in the ensemble, which are identified in the as

> **trial_<ensemble_method><source ID>**, for example > **trial_CMT_ClustMedian**. Moreover, two other folders are also > created, **salvus_post_swarm** and **salvus_plot**, where the > output data and the final figures are created. The figures are > compressed and uploaded to the HPC data repository. Inside each > **trial_<ensemble_method><source ID>** folder, 4 > subfolders area created: **slipgen**, **salvus_wrapper**, **salvus**, and > **salvus_plots** with the corresponding slurm file.

image1 Figure 7. Folder and file structure defined in including the salvus_wrapperMN5

IV. Developer

In this section a guide to develop and deploy a new microservices, and to define a new regions in UCIS4EQ are described.

4.1 How to add a new region?

Adding a new region is easy, but it has to be done manually, so it is necessary not to make mistakes in the steps in order not to produce typos or an incorrect definition of the necessary values. Fig. 8 highlights those folders and files that must be created (green) or updated (orange) to include the information of a new region. From top to bottom, in Fig. 8:

4.1.1. HCP data repository:

-

1. In the *StaticDataMapping.json* the information related to the new > Regions must be included. For example, if we want to add the > “CALIFORNIA” region, we need to define two new elements in the file > as json keys, **CALIFORNIA_DATA** and **CALIFORNIA**:

image25 image27

In **CALIFORNIA_DATA**, the metadata and the path to the data are located at the HPC-site is defined. In **CALIFORNIA** key is mapped to the data located at the HPC data repository.

2. *Setup/DALv2/Regions.json* file must include the data of the new > region, for example:

image20

Figure 1: image20

•

In the path `/Data/Regions/<NewRegion>`, `<NewRegion>` must be substituted by the name of the new region, for example `/Data/Regions/California/`. **The name of this new folder must agree with the `/Setup/DALV2/Regions.json` ID name.** Also, you can validate the structure of the JSON files through a free online validator (e.g. <https://jsononline.net/json-validator>), to avoid mistakes that may affect other users. The four new subfolders detailed in the previous section must be created, including the configuration files and required data in each subfolder:

RECEIVERS, SLIP_GEN, SOURCE ENSEMBLE, and INFERENCE_TYPE if ML models are available for that region

4.1.2 HPC-site:

•

To set a new region is also mandatory to create the folders in the corresponding HPC machine. Those folders are structured following the structure found on `DataStructure.json` in the HPC data repository. The needed files correspond to the bathymetry, topography, and 3D velocity models and numerical meshes. In the current example for MN4 must be included in the following path:

» `/gpfs/projects/bsc44/earthquake/UCIS4EQ/data/`

MED_SAMOS_IZMIR

BATHYMETRY

`bathymetry_earth2014_lmax_10800.nc -> /gpfs/projects/bsc44/earthquake/UCIS4EQ/data/GLOBE`

MESHES

MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_1.5Hz.h5

MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_1.5Hz.xdmf

MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_5.0Hz.h5

image29

Figure 2: image29

```
MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_5.0Hz.xdmf
TOPOGRAPHY
  grid_topo_file_1p5Hz.nc
  topography_earth2014_egm2008_lmax_10800.nc -> /gpfs/projects/bsc44/earthquake/UCIS4EQ/d
VELOCITY_MODEL
  SamosIzmir_mod_csem_eastmed.nc
```

Other files needed for the use case: The `salvus_urgent_wrapper` can help you generate files for a use case. I was setting it up ages ago for manual testing with the YAML files that were provided to me by Juane from UCIS4EQ, so it needs a YAML file that resembles the UCIS4EQ yaml parameter file.

The things that need to be correctly specified in the YAML file are:

The `generate_mesh` flag needs to be set to "yes" if you want the scripts to output a mesh. The `fmax_in_hz` and `geometry` are needed for generating the mesh, specifying the max resolution, the spatial extent, and the file paths, respectively. The file paths point to where the mesh will be saved (`mesh_onthefly`), and what velocity model to use (`velocity_model`: either a Salvus-compatible file or "csem", in which case it will use CSEM), and what topography and bathymetry files to use.

The `CMT_source` needs to be specified for generating the 1D model for This specific location will be used for the Graves and Pitarka rupture generator.

1. Generate a 1D model for Graves Pitarka

1. First, you need to download CRUST1.0

2. Then you need to specify the paths to the downloaded CRUST1.0 vp, vs and rho netcdf files in

```
salvus_urgent_wrapper/utils/generate_1d_velocity_profile_for_GravesPitarka.py
```

3. And finally, you have to run the Python script specifying the path to the UCIS4EQ yaml file (`-u`) and then the path to where the model will be output as a text file in the right format for Graves Pitarka (`-o`). The things that it reads from the YAML file are the latitude and the longitude of the CMT solution.

```
python /path/to/salvus_urgent_wrapper/utils/generate_1d_velocity_profile_for_GravesPitarka.py
-u
```

```
/path/to/ucis4eq_yaml_file.yaml -o /path/to/outputting/crust1p0.1d
```

2. Generate mesh

The script for preprocessing used in UCIS4EQ can also generate meshes. This means that UCIS4EQ can potentially also

generate meshes on-the-fly, but this is not how it is set up now on the UCIS4EQ end - you have to give it static paths to specific use case meshes. However, we can manually call the pre-processing script with the YAML file that resembles what UCIS4EQ produces (-u) and force it to generate a mesh that we then have to put in the right place. The script also needs the `salvus_parameters.yaml` file that UCIS4EQ uses for pre-processing. Be careful about the file name (specified as `mesh_on_the_fly` in the yaml file, or you can change it when moving it to the cluster. It needs to include the frequency as a float, e.g. `MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_5.0Hz.h5`

You run:

```
salvus_urgent_wrapper/salvus_urgent_wrapper/salvus_preprocess/salvus_preprocess.py  
-u
```

```
/path/to/ucis4eq_yaml_file.yaml -s /path/to/salvus_parameters.yaml
```

4.1.3 GitLab:

-

When a new region is included, a new JSON file with the basic information must be created in the GitLab repository. This is for the cases when a trigger manually uses a use case of the Workflow that is done by using the curl command:

```
» curl -X POST -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d @/path/to/use_case.json  
http://127.0.0.1:5001/PyCOMPSsWM
```

image3 (a)

image21 (b)

image2 (c) Fig. 8 The three code/data repositories structures are highlighted in green color those folders/files that must be created when a new region is added, and in orange, those folders/files that must be modified.

4.2 How to include a new microservice?

This section describes the steps needed to include a new microservice in UCIS4EQ. The changes must be done mainly in GitLab and HPC data (Fig. 4 and 7). Figures 9 and 10 highlight in orange the folders and files that are

image34

Figure 3: image34

image39

Figure 4: image39

updated and/or changed, and in green those boxes where files and/or folders must be created.

As an example of creating a new microservice, we will use the steps taken in the creation of the MLESmap microservice. However, depending on the functionality of the new microservice, the Python code added in the **components/code/** will be different.

4.2.1 GitLab:

Figure 9 and Table 1 summarize the changes in files and folders that must be made in the GitLab code to include the new microservices. Each row summarizes the main changes in each file.

Figure 9

Following, we will describe in detail some indications of each modified or created a file.

1. **code/services/scc/mlesMapService.py**

This file was created, including the main steps indicated in Fig. 10

image41 Figure 10. mlesMapService creation in code/services/mlesMapService.py

2. **code/components/scc/mlesmapInference.py**

This file is generated from scratch, defining all the classes the new microservice will have to do. This microservice will be called from the workflowManager.py, which will be described in the next section.

The new function must be created in *code/components/scc* in this example name mlesmapInference

*** Import Modules and Functions:***

[The modules used must be included in the Docker File of the microservice], also created for setting a new microservice. [] In this example

Class Event:

image28

Figure 5: image28

image40

Figure 6: image40

In this example, we need to define the Event class to set the parameters that will have the output JSON file in the mlesInference class. In this case, it defines the parameters that the JSON output will have and that will be the input of the MLESmap to make the inference.

Class mlesSetup:

This class connects the microservice with the HPC data repository to download the configuration defined folder corresponding to the one that has the MLESmap service. All changes made in the HPC data are explained in the following section. The inputs that are received are always in json format and are defined in the workflowManager.py code

Class mlesInference:

In our example, in this class, the ML inference is executed using the models located in the HPC data in this class, using a private function named `_getMLESmap`. The ML models located in the HPC data are loaded

Class mlesMapPlot:

In this class, the plot is generated for the values inferred in the previous class and uploaded to the HPC data repository. This class uses the private function named `_getPlots`.

3. data/CALIFORNIA.json

It is important to mention that in the example, we use a hardcoded file in which a new keyword “**MLinference**”: “**mlesmap**” has been incorporated to indicate that the MLESmap services should be started as shown in the following screenshot.

image42

Figure 7: image42

image43

Figure 8: image43

image24

Figure 9: image24

4. `code/components/scc/workflowManger.py`

In this script, many modifications have been made to some calls or services to make the new microservice work (MLEsmap). Then the `workflowManger.py` script will react to this keyword defined in the listener or hardcoded triggering file. The following screenshot shows two parts of the `workflowManger.py` script where this new microservice must be incorporated.

The keyword is read from the input JSON file, where the triggering event Data is stored and passed as a parameter

```
inference= body['MLinference']
```

The *inference* parameter is passed to the *get_setup* microservice, and the information will be passed in the *setup* variable

In this **if** statement, the *inference* keyword verifies that it is 'mlesmap' and triggers the corresponding microservices described above.

In the final section of the `workflowManager.py` script, PyCOMPSs defines the workload and other parameters

needed by the orchestrator. These parameters are similar to those received in a normal Python function

but must be defined in the following structure for each class within the MLEsmap microservice called in

this script. Those parameters' names will structure the body that is the input in each class, considering the same

ID word.

5. `data/project.xml` and `data/resources.xml`

In these files, the port of the new microservices must be included as shown in the following screenshots. Those port numbers are defined in `code/services/scc/mlesMapService.py`

image22

Figure 10: image22

image14

Figure 11: image14

image5

Figure 12: image5

6. deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-mlesMapServices

A new Dockerfile must be created for the new microservice. It is a simple text file with a set of commands or instructions. These commands/instructions are executed successively to perform actions on the base image to create a new Docker image. In this file, the required packages for the microservice are defined.

After its creation, the following command must be run to generate the docker image

```
docker build -f deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-mlesMapServices -t registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/mlesMap .
```

7. ~/docker-compose.yml, > ~/docker-compose-add-ssh-key-to-docker.yml, > ~/docker-compose-build.yml, ~/docker-compose-debug.yml

4.2.2 HPC data :

1. StaticDataMapping.json

It is important to update this file to include the new region (see Section: How to include a new region?) and the name of the microservice available for that region. In the example, three microservices must be included: **mlesSetup**, **mlesInference**, **mlesMapPlots**, if those are not defined the microservice will not work.

image26

Figure 13: image26

image27

Figure 14: image27

image31

Figure 15: image31

2. Data/Region name with the available data for the microservice, in > the example CALIFORNIA

In this case a new folder is included to save the data and metadata required in the microservice

The region that offers the microservice must have the files required by the microservice. In the example are: **mlesmap.json**, **scaler_X.save**, **scaler_Y.save**, **NN_model.h5**. The first file has the metadata of the models and scalers used in the service.

3. Setup/DalV2/DataStructure.json

4. Setup/DalV2/Regions.json

Similarly, the HPC data repository requires important changes in some files, as shown in Figure 10 and summarized in Table 2

Figure 10

4.3 How to include a new machine?

→ data/Sites.json

→ code/components/launchers/

→ HPC data changes

4.4. Prepare new use case

For the below, you need the `salvus_urgent_wrapper` package on a machine with enough RAM to generate the mesh, and if you want to use the [CSEM] models,

image33

Figure 16: image33

image36

Figure 17: image36

image32

Figure 18: image32

then you need to download the CSEM models and have an installation of the csem lib Python package to extract the models onto the mesh. You will need the ETH SWP group to help you set it up.

4.4.1 Generate files for the use case

The `salvus_urgent_wrapper` can help you generate files for a use case. I was setting it up ages ago for manual testing with the YAML files that were provided to me by Juan Esteban from UCIS4EQ, so it needs a YAML file that resembles the UCIS4EQ YAML parameter file.

The things that need to be correctly specified in the YAML file are:

```
fmax\_in\_hz: \"5\"
generate\_mesh: \"yes\"
geometry:
  coordinates:
    min\_latitude: \"37.51\"
    max\_latitude: \"38.76\"
    min\_longitude: \"26.12\"
    max\_longitude: \"27.36\"
    depth\_in\_m: \"50e3\"
  filepaths:
    mesh\_onthe-fly: \"/path/to/where/the/mesh/is/saved/mesh.h5\"
    velocity\_model: \"csem\"
    topography: \"/path/to/topography\_earth2014\_egm2008\_lmax\_10800.nc\"
    bathymetry: \"/path/to/bathymetry\_earth2014\_lmax\_10800.nc\"
  CMT\_source:
    longitude: \"26.6300\"
    latitude: \"37.7800\"
```

The `generate_mesh` flag needs to be set to "yes" if you want the scripts to out-

image18

Figure 19: image18

put a mesh. The `fmax_in_hz` and `geometry` are needed for generating the mesh, specifying the max resolution, and the spatial extent, and the file paths, respectively. The file paths point to where the mesh will be saved (`mesh_onthefly`), what velocity model to use (`velocity_model`: either a Salvus-compatible file or "csem", in which case it will use CSEM), and what topography and bathymetry files to use.

The `CMT_source` needs to be specified for generating the 1D model for this specific location that will be used for the Graves-Pitarka rupture generator.

4.4.2. Generate a 1D model for Graves Pitarka

1. First, you need to download `> [CRUST1.0]`
2. Then you need to specify the paths to the downloaded CRUST1.0 `vp, vs >` and `rho netcdf` files in `> salvus_urgent_wrapper/utils/generate_1d_velocity_profile_for_GravesPitarka.`
3. And finally, you have to run the Python script specifying the path to `>` the UCIS4EQ `yaml` file (`-u`) and then the path to where the model `>` will be output as a text file in the right format for Graves `>` Pitarka (`-o`). The things that it reads from the `YAML` file are the `>` latitude and the longitude of the CMT solution.

```
python
/path/to/salvus\_urgent\_wrapper/utils/generate\_1d\_velocity\_profile\_for\_GravesPitarka.p
-u /path/to/ucis4eq\_yaml\_file.yaml -o /path/to/outputting/crust1p0.1d
```

4.4.3 Generate mesh

The script for preprocessing used in UCIS4EQ can also generate meshes. This means that UCIS4EQ can potentially also generate meshes on-the-fly, but this is not how it is set up now on the UCIS4EQ end - you have to give it static paths to specific use case meshes. However, we can manually call the pre-processing script with the `YAML` file that resembles what UCIS4EQ produces (`-u`) and force it to generate a mesh that we then have to put in the right place. The script also needs the `salvus_parameters.yaml` file that UCIS4EQ uses for preprocessing.

Be careful about the file name (specified as `mesh_on_the_fly` in the `yaml` file, or you can change it when moving it to the cluster. It needs to include the frequency as a float, e.g., `MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_5.0Hz.h5`

You run:

```
salvus\_urgent\_wrapper/salvus\_urgent\_wrapper/salvus\_preprocess/salvus\_preprocess.py
-u /path/to/ucis4eq\_yaml\_file.yaml -s /path/to/salvus\_parameters.yaml
```

4.4.4 Add information to UCIS4EQ

1. Specify region in Regions.json with the id being the REGION_NAME.
 - The dimensions of the region correspond to the dimensions of the > mesh that you have generated above (so to the > [geometry][coordinates] in the yaml file).
 - The frequency corresponds to the fmax. Here is an important note on > frequency: right now, the frequency simulation policy is > hard-coded by Juane (ucis4eq/code/components/scc/event.py > line 220) to be the maximum available frequency. So if you > have generated two meshes for the same region, at 1Hz and 3Hz, > and you add both in Regions.json, then UCIS4EQ will by default > always pick 3Hz. Best to put just one in Regions.json, as I > think only the options for changing the frequency policy are > minimum available and maximum available.
 - The available_ensemble is about choosing the way in which the > set of sources is calculated. Right now, it is only > StatisticalCMT is available, so you have to put that.
1. Add region in the StaticDataMapping.json file:
 - the REGION_NAME entry points to what is on HPC data : > (BATHYMETRY, MESHES, TOPOGRAPHY, VELOCITY_MODEL)
 - the REGION_NAME_DATA entry points to what is on Daint > (RECEIVERS , SLIP_GEN , SOURCE_ENSEMBLE)
2. Add all files on the HPC cluster in the data folder of the UCIS4EQ > installation, that is in UCIS4EQ/data/REGION_NAME (see below the > mesh generation) Here the subfolders are: VELOCITY_MODEL : empty, > then we assume it's been CSEM TOPOGRAPHY : symlink to global topo > file just for reference BATHYMETRY : symlink to global bathy file > just for reference MESHES : note that the file name must include > the max frequency as a float (e.g. 5.0) in the file name, as this > is how the code checks if the right file is there.

3. Add all files on HPC data in the corresponding folder in > UCIS4EQ/data/REGION_NAME
 RECEIVERS : the Receivers.json file that > includes receiver locations
 SLIP_GEN : needs the GPSetup.json > file with the fmax as a float in the
 file name (e.g. 5.0) and the > 1d model for GP SOURCE_ENSEMBLE :
 right now for Marisol's method > we need a statisticalCMT.json file with
 parameters and the .xml > catalog (downloadable from > here). Best
 just model it > on one of the existing use cases!
4. Prepare the event.json file that you pass to the curl command > afterwards.
 Note that the time and the magnitude need to be those > that correspond
 to what is in the .xml catalog, so that this > specific event can be filtered
 out from the catalog of past events > when we look at other events in the
 region (to ensure proper > testing, because of course, a new event that
 would trigger the > system would not be in the catalog in the first place
 :)).
5. Remember to adjust the resources in the Sites.json file for each > test case
 relative to the mesh size! (Very annoying, sorry.)

Note: if you want to perform a dry run of the service without submitting any jobs, comment out all submission.run commands in UCIS4EQ and run the services in debug mode (which means that the code itself is loaded at runtime in the Docker, overriding what is in the Docker image, see the relevant section in the Installation PDF). Then, if you submit the event.json script to the service, all it will do is generate all submission scripts and input files on the cluster without submitting jobs. This option is available only to those who have the UCIS4EQ source code installed locally. `docker compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up salvus slipgen microservices docker compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up workflowmanager`

4.5 Push to GitLab repository a docker image built in local

1. Docker images → To find the name of the image that wants to be > uploaded
2. `docker login gitlab.bsc.es` (if your password doesn't work you need > to create an access token in your personal GitLab settings "Access > Token" and use it in place of the GitLab password)
3. `docker tag > registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/mlesmap:latest > registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/mlesmap:v1.0`
4. `docker push > [registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/mlesmap:v1.0]`
5. To verify that the image is uploaded in GitLab

Go to "Packages & Registries", and search the option "Packages & Registries". Finally, look in "Container Registry".

V. Install & Deployment

5.1. Installation

5.1.1 Dependencies

First, you have to install docker and docker compose (docker engine) [<https://docs.docker.com/install/linux/docker-ce/ubuntu/>]

Then make sure you can run docker without sudo: [<https://docs.docker.com/engine/install/linux-postinstall/>]

If you cannot or do not want to run without sudo, you will have to run with the `-E` flag to make sure that you preserve the environment variables (i.e. all docker compose commands below have to be preceded with `sudo -E`).

Note: That's not exactly a dependency, but you also need to have the SSH keys set up for the machine where you will be running simulations and also the `SSH_AUTH_SOCK` environment variable needs to be defined (should be automatic, but it turns out that it does not work for all Linux distributions).

5.1.2 UCIS4EQ services

1. Because the Docker images are registered on a GitLab repository, > first you have to do the login. `-p` specifies the password, and `>` is the project access token for a private project. It will ask you > to provide your GitLab username. This is not the e-mail address > that you use for login, but the actual @username.

```
docker login registry.gitlab.com -p glpat-2fr-PF8pNpCErgeTyR31
```

2. Then create a UCIS4EQ working directory, move there and run:

```
bash -c \"\$(curl --request GET --header 'PRIVATE-TOKEN:
glpat-75-FV88yWpzpCZJvoKfe'
\[https://gitlab.com/api/v4/projects/43953314/repository/files/install.sh/raw?ref=marta\_c
```

This downloads and runs the install.sh script from a private repo.

3. Set your own credentials in DAL.json:

1. For BSC_HPC data, change just the user and pass fields.
2. If you are on Marenstrum4, change the user and the path. The > path is the folder for runs and is probably going to be in > your scratch.
3. If you are on Daint, change the user, the proxy, and the path. > The path is the folder for runs and is probably going to be in > your scratch.

3. Set your own credentials in Sites.json:

1. If you're on Daint, just keep Daint and remove MN4, and vice > versa. There is some sort of priority system for which machine > to choose if both are defined, but it is just a manually set > index for now (in one of the config files that are on HPC data > , so it is *the same for all users...* not ideal...). So to > avoid confusion, just keep a single one.
2. Set your user and your path again (make it the same as in > DAL.json - I think one of those is just a legacy thing and is > not read, but I actually do not know which one that is), and > the proxy if on Daint.
3. Then there are the resources. They are set for the small test > case that we are going to run. This is some sort of temporary > solution that was set up before a proper resource allocation > is in place - it is far from ideal, as you have to adjust this > now for every test case (that is, mostly the wtime, nodes, and > tasks-per-node for the SalvusRun itself).
4. To run you have to make sure that the machine/cluster you're > meaning to work on has the ssh key set up with the localhost and > that it has been added to the ~/.ssh/known_hosts file. Also > check that the SSH_AUTH_SOCKET variable is defined (run echo > \$SSH_AUTH_SOCKET and see if it outputs something) - it should be > automatically defined if you have an SSH agent installed, but it > turns out that on some distributions it is not and you have to do > it yourself (e.g. Arch Linux).

When you run for the first time, run:

```
docker compose up
```

It will download the images and run all the services. Note that depending on your docker compose installation, your command might be docker-compose (rather than docker compose).

For running in a "regular" way, I recommend that you run in two separate terminal windows:

```
docker compose up slipgen salvus microservices
```

and

```
docker compose up workflowmanager
```

This way you have a better overview of what is happening in the services. If you run all together, the workflowmanager output will dominate and it is harder to find your way through the on-screen log.

If you have set everything up correctly and run the two docker compose up commands above, the outputs should look like this:

Note that this does not start up the listener service for automatic submissions, but just the containers needed for manual submissions. If you want to see the listener in action, start it up (in a separate terminal window) with

```
docker compose up listener
```

6. To stop running the services hit ctrl+C twice in all terminal > windows where services are running, and to properly clean up run > (in just one window):

```
docker compose down
```

Note: an alternative way of adding SSH keys to the dockers

If things worked for you and your SSH connection works when you run, you can ignore this. :-)

Some of the services need to be able to establish an SSH connection to the cluster, so the docker images need to have the ssh key set up. The docker images that are pulled from the container registry do not have any ssh keys, and by running the docker compose up command you use the docker-compose.yml file which mounts two things from the localhost to the containers at runtime:

1. The SSH_AUTH_SOCK environment variable.
2. The ~/.ssh/known_hosts file. This should work on a Linux machine > and on a Mac one (tested on both). I am not sure if this works on > a Windows machine and the internet suggests that it may not. In > any case, **this method is safe, as it does not permanently add > the SSH keys anywhere and just mounts the local ones at runtime.**

If, for some reason it does not work, you can use another deployment option which builds an extra layer to the images that require the SSH connection (this is the original way in which Juan Esteban set this up). Those images are local and you should be **careful to not upload them anywhere, as they contain your private SSH key!**

If you are on Daint run (where PD_USER is your Piz Daint username):

```
SSH\_PRV="\$(cat ~/.ssh/private\_key\_name)" PD\_USER="username"
docker compose -f docker-compose-add-ssh-key-to-docker.yml up
```

or if you are on MN4 run:

```
SSH\_PRV="\$(cat ~/.ssh/private\_key\_name)" docker compose -f
docker-compose-add-ssh-key-to-docker.yml up
```

Then, for all subsequent runs, you can do (as above) in two separate terminal windows:

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-add-ssh-key-to-docker.yml up slipgen
salvus microservices
```

and

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-add-ssh-key-to-docker.yml up
workflowmanager
```

This will run the re-built images instead of the basic ones which mount the ssh information at runtime.

5.1.3 Setting up on a new machine

The above assumes that you are using an installation on the HPC cluster that already is there and ready.

If this is not the case, a new cluster needs to be set up.

On the cluster itself:

1. slipgen.simg
2. salvus_urgent_wrapper (private git repo) + python environment with > dependencies
3. data folder with regions (currently region = use case; later ideally > regions will be significantly larger meshes that we will mask for > simulations); in each folder there are four subfolders: BATHYMETRY > , MESHES , TOPOGRAPHY, VELOCITY_MODEL

In the code:

1. need to add a machinenameRunner.py script with the setup of > preparing the submission scripts in > ucis4eq/code/components/launchers

In the setup:

1. add machine to Sites.json and DAL.json (local machine)
2. add machine to HPC data in:
 - UCIS4EQ/Setup/DALv2/Repositories.json
 - UCIS4EQ/Setup/DALv2/Resources.json

5.1.4 Only for developments: running in debug mode and building new images

This might be trivial to some, but I am including this as a note for future reference for the "scientific" developers like me who do science and try their best to code, but get demoralised when confronted with proper code and proper software developers ;-)

a) Debug mode If you have access to the source code and you have changed something, you can first test it without the necessity of re-building the images.

If you run in two separate terminal windows:

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up slipgen salvus
microservices
```

and

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up workflowmanager
```

you are going to mount the local code (with the changes you have implemented) into the docker containers at runtime. This means that the old UCIS4EQ that was included in the docker images gets overwritten with your local version. If you want to check if the debugging mode worked as expected, you can run `docker ps` to list the running containers (after you have put up the services with the up commands above) and then enter the container to explore what is inside by running:

```
docker exec -it container-name bash
```

You can see the container-name in the output of the `docker ps` command.

b) Rebuild images If you are then sure that you want to include that addition into the images, you can rebuild them. I would first run:

```
docker images
```

to list the images and see their IDs. Then:

```
docker rmi -f imageID1 imageID2 ...
```

where imageIDs are the IDs of the UCIS4EQ images.

This way you remove the old images (I am not sure if this is absolutely necessary or not, but I was doing this to be on the safe side), and then you can rebuild them by running:

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-build.yml build
```

Note that this is going to take a while (~2h or so).

Finally, you have to push the new containers to the repository:

```
docker compose -f docker-compose-build.yml push
```

This assumes that you are logged in via `docker login registry.gitlab.com` and that you have the right to push images to the repo.

5.2 Run existing use case

This assumes that everything is set up for the use case on the given cluster where you want to just execute it.

5.2.1 - Start the services

Navigate to the directory where you installed UCIS4EQ (and where docker-compose.yml is sitting). Then run in two different terminal windows:

```
docker compose up salvus slipgen microservices
```

```
docker compose up workflowmanager
```

This way you don't the listener service, and also you get to see the outputs more clearly (as the workflowmanager generates a lot of output.)

5.2.2 - Trigger a manual alert

First, make sure that the resources in Sites.json are specified correctly for the event you want to run. Also, make sure that you're going to right the fmax that you'd like (see the 2. Prepare new use case PDF about the Regions.json file in HPC data and the "frequency policy").

Then, in yet another terminal window run:

```
curl -X POST -H \'Content-Type: application/json\' -d  
@/path/to/use\_case.json http://127.0.0.1:5001/PyCOMPSsWM
```

You have an example use case json file in ucis4eq/data/MED_SAMOS_IZMIR_IRIS_test.json

5.2.3 - Event follow-up in the Dashboard

Open a browser and go to <http://127.0.0.1:8050/>

5.3. Salvus on MN5

The Salvus installation on Marenostrom5 is maintained at

```
SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR=/gpfs/projects/bsc21/WPG/Earthquake/Ucis4eq/Resources/Salvus/
```

This includes a node-locked SalvusCompute binary at `${SALVUS_INSTALL_DIR}/Salvus-2025/bin/salvus`

and the Salvus Python wheel in

```
\${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/Salvus-2025/python\_packages
```

To use this version of Salvus, all simulation scripts should point to the Salvus-Compute binary specified above. Furthermore, a Python environment with an installation of the Salvus wheel is required. A shared conda environment can be created using the following snippet:

```
\# Make sure the system-wide installation of anaconda is loaded
```

```
module load anaconda
```

```

\# Download the list of Python dependencies for Salvus

wget https://docs.mondaic.com/environment-py311.yml -O
\${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/environment-py311.yml

\# Create a new Python environment with the Salvus dependencies

mkdir -p \${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/conda

conda env create -p \${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/conda/salvus-2025 -f
\${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/environment-py311.yml

\# Activate the environment

conda activate \${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/conda/salvus-2025

\# Install the Salvus Python wheel

pip install \${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/Salvus-2025/python\_packages/\*whl

To access this environment in a job script, either the 'PATH' variable needs to
be prepended with:

export PATH=\${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/conda/salvus-2025/bin:\$PATH

Alternatively, the environment can be activated using:

module load anaconda

conda activate \${SALVUS\_INSTALL\_DIR}/conda/salvus-2025

```

VI. Launch

```
HPC\_RUN\_PYCOMPSS=true docker-compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up
workflowmanager
```

```
curl -X POST -H 'Content-Type: application/json' -d
\@data/MED\_SAMOS\_IZMIR\_test.json
[[http://127.0.0.1:5001/PyCOMPSSWM]] (http://127.0.0.1:5001/PyCOMPSSWM)
```

VI. References

- [1] E. Daniell James, M. Schaefer, and F. Wenzel, Losses associated with secondary effects in earthquakes. *Frontiers in Built Environment* 3 (2017), 30.
- [2] Wald, D. J., Worden, C. B., Quitariano, V., & Goltz, J. (2002). Shakemap: its role in pre-earthquake planning and post-earthquake response and informa-

tion. In Proceedings SMIP02 Seminar on Utilization of Strong-Motion Data (pp. 1-20).

[3] de la Puente, J., Rodriguez, J. E., Monterrubio-Velasco, M., Rojas, O., & Folch, A. (2020, June). Urgent Supercomputing of Earthquakes: Use Case for Civil Protection. In Proceedings of the Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing Conference (pp. 1-8).

[4] Ejarque, J., Monterrubio-Velasco, M., Bhihe, C., Pienkowska, M., De La Puente, J., & Badia, R. M. (2024, November). Managing Workflow Malleability in Urgent Computing for Earthquake Alerts. In SC24-W: Workshops of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis (pp. 2064-2071). IEEE.

VII. APENDIX

A1. Delete “SUCCESS” files

After the execution of a step in the HPC a ‘SUCCESS’ file is created. In case it is needed to re-run an workflow execution, UCIS4EQ is prepared to execute the same exercise without start from the beginning, and continue where the not SUCCESS file is found. So, if the user wants to delete the SUCCESS file just you need to write this

```
find . -type d -name \'salvus\' -exec find {} -type f -name \'SUCCESS\'  
-print \\\;
```

```
find . -type d -name \'salvus\' -exec find \'{\}\' -type f -name  
\'SUCCESS\' -delete \\\;
```

A2. Instructions for running the old version of UCIS4EQ with the WFEEmulator

General instructions to execute the ucis4eq in a local machine

```
docker-compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up microServices slipGen
```

```
docker-compose -f docker-compose-debug.yml up workflowManager
```

\#Para ejecutar el ejemplo

\#1. Entrar en data/

```
/home/mmonterr/Documentos/CHEESE/PD1/ucis4eq/data
```

\# y ejecutar

```
curl -X POST -H \'Content-Type: application/json\' -d
```

```
\@SISZ\_EQEventExample.json http://127.0.0.1:5001/WMEulator
```

```
\# o directamente.
```

```
curl -X POST -H \'Content-Type: application/json\' -d  
\@data/SISZ\_EQEventExample.json http://127.0.0.1:5001/WMEulator
```

A3. Instructions for adding more Python packages pip install in the docker file.

After open the dockerfile of the microservice where you want to add another python package, you must build that dockerfile:

```
\# For example, if it is a package that is used exclusively in  
microservices it is in Dockerfile-microservices.
```

```
docker build -f deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-microServices -t  
registry.gitlab.com/cheese-coe/ucis4eq/microservices .
```

```
\# If it is a more general package used in a more than an specific  
microservices, you must intall in Dockerfile-base and after it build the  
Dockerfile-base
```

```
docker build -f deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-base -t  
registry.gitlab.com/cheese-coe/ucis4eq/base .
```

```
\# In case you have problems can also force rebuild from the base and  
label it develop:\
```

```
\  
docker build -f deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-base -t  
registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/base:develop .
```

And then rebuild the microservices point it to that base

```
\  
docker build -f deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-microServices \\  
--build-arg
```

```
IMAGE=registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/base:develop \\  
-t
```

```
registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/microservices:develop  
.
```

Run the microservices container and verify that Flask is installed:

```
docker run -it \--rm  
registry.gitlab.bsc.es/wavephenomenagroup/ucis4eq/microservices:develop
```

```
python -c "import flask; print(flask.__version__)"
```

A4. Old microservices ... Instructions for deploying the indexPriority microservice

```
\# En docker-compose-debug.yml se agregaron dos variables de entorno mas, una que tiene que ver con el path a las bases de datos que se utilizan en la funcion indexPriority y la otra con el archivo de json que contiene los nombres de cada uno de las bases de datos config.indexPriority.json que
```

```
\- \${UCIS4EQ\_IPRIORITY\_DATA}:/root/data/indexPriority/
```

```
\- \${UCIS4EQ\_IPRIORITY\_CONFIG}:/root/data/config\_indexPriority.json
```

```
\#\# Haciendo control+h aparecen los archivos ocultos. En el archivo .env agregar el path local para que funcionen las pruebas en mi ordenador:
```

```
\# Index priority data
```

```
UCIS4EQ\_IPRIORITY\_DATA=/home/mmonterr/Documentos/CHEESE/PD1/ucis4eq/data/indexPriority/
```

```
UCIS4EQ\_IPRIORITY\_CONFIG=/home/mmonterr/Documentos/CHEESE/PD1/ucis4eq/data/config\_indexP
```

A5. To download a new version of Docker-base

```
docker pull registry.gitlab.com/cheese-coe/ucis4eq/base
```

```
docker build -f deployment/dockers/Dockerfile-microServices -t registry.gitlab.com/cheese-coe/ucis4eq/microservices .
```

A6. To access the docker meanwhile is up

```
docker ps
```

```
docker exec -ti \<tuID\> bash
```

```
# For example,\....
```

```
docker exec -ti workdir\_microservices\_1 bash
```